

Report on Third Round of Benchmarks Deliverable D3.9

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Author Information

Name	Organisation	E-mail
Javier Sanz Rodrigo	CENER	jsrodrigo@cener.com
Roberto Chávez	CENER	rchavez@cener.com
Julia Gottschall	Fraunhofer IWES	julia.gottschall@iwes.fraunhofer.de
Martin Dörenkämper	Fraunhofer IWES	martin.doerenkaemper@iwes.fraunhofer.de
Björn Witha	ForWind – University of Oldenburg	bjoern.witha@forwind.de

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Executive Summary

This report summarizes the third round of benchmarks conducted under the NEWA validation strategy [1].

The **first round** of microscale benchmarks [2] was directed to developing microscale models that can be driven with mesoscale input forcing, include thermal stratification of the atmospheric boundary layer and high resolution digital models of heterogeneous forest canopy characteristics based on aerial lidar-scan data. These fundamental implementations were developed around the GABLS3 diurnal-cycle and Ryningsnäs forest canopy benchmarks, both in flat terrain conditions. By model intercomparison, NEWA modelers found reasonably good consistency in the simulation of these cases, establishing common understanding of the modeling capabilities of the group before attempting more complex simulation challenges in connection to the NEWA experiments.

The **second round** of benchmarks [3] focused on flow modeling over forested terrain based on the Rödeser Berg and Hornamossen experiments to add terrain complexity to the baseline settings used in GABLS3 and Ryningsnäs. A follow-up benchmark from GABLS3, based at the Cabauw tower, served to launch the “NEWA Meso-Micro Challenge for Wind Resource Assessment” to address the evaluation of a hierarchy of methodologies that incorporate mesoscale-to-microscale downscaling and understand the added-value compared to traditional approaches for site assessment that rely only on microscale modeling.

The **third round** continues with the second phase of the challenge in complex terrain, starting with Rödeser Berg. Following the NEWA validation strategy the benchmarks will be directed to flow cases targeting the validation of specific phenomena, as well as case studies that integrate these models in wind resource assessment methodologies to assess the impact on relevant quantities of interest for the wind industry such as annual energy prediction, site assessment characteristics, mean profiles, etc.

Additionally, the Ferry Lidar benchmark was launched to test mesoscale models predicting the wind profile along a ship track in the Southern Baltic Sea.

With the NEWA project concluded, the meso-micro challenge will continue in the frame of the **IEA-Wind Task 31 “Wakebench”** as new benchmarks are generated from the database of experiments [4].

Introduction

The NEWA validation strategy is covered in [1], the first round of benchmarks in [2] and the second round in [3]. NEWA experimental data and benchmarking activities are leveraged to the international community under the umbrella of the IEA-Wind Task 31 *Wakebench*. This allows engaging with a wider range of researchers and models and supports the integration of NEWA model evaluation procedures in Task 31 Model Evaluation Protocol [4].

The verification and validation (V&V) framework established in Task 31 is based on the one developed at Sandia National Laboratories [5] which, itself, follows existing methodologies developed by various American organizations including the American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA) [6] and the American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME) [7]. The framework is briefly introduced here to explain how NEWA contributes to fill the building blocks for the validation of models for the assessment of wind conditions.

1. NEWA Validation Building Blocks for Wind Conditions

1.1. The Wakebench V&V Framework

The segmented pyramid of Figure 1 is used in the Wakebench framework [4] to represent the relationships between different building blocks of the validation framework in terms of atmospheric and wind power system scales.

Figure 1: System scales and phenomena of interest for "wind" (right, dark grey hierarchy) and "wake" conditions (left, light grey hierarchy) [8].

A hierarchy of increasing flow complexity is established as higher levels of coupling between relevant physical phenomena are added towards a full system validation. In practice, full system validation is not possible though because this would require

experiments in all operational conditions. Instead, the evaluation process aims at improving model credibility to mitigate uncertainties in the prediction of relevant quantities for the application of interest.

A V&V framework facilitates discussions between the scientific community and industry to identify the knowledge gaps (experiments, model development and validation) that should be addressed with higher priority to improve the predictive capacity of models. Consensus on relevant phenomena for wind farm models in view of their validation track record is formulated in a Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table (PIRT) which is utilized as a planning tool to guide the validation strategy [1].

1.2. NEWA Validation Building Blocks for Wind Conditions

The coupling of mesoscale and microscale models implies drastic changes in the implementation of microscale models that can benefit from more realistic transient boundary conditions, as opposed to using steady-state canonical inflow conditions. However, general adoption by industry requires a cost-benefit justification by comparing with current engineering models. The NEWA "Meso-Micro Challenge" is addressing this opportunity based on a suite of validation datasets derived from experiments in a range of site and wind climate conditions, from homogeneous (Cabauw, Fino1) to heterogeneous flows due to terrain and vegetation changes (Ryningsnäs, Rödeser Berg, Hornamossen, Perdigao and Alaiz) [9].

Figure 2: Building-block hierarchy for the validation of wind-conditions models and associated NEWA experiments addressing relevant phenomena of interest.

Figure 2 expands the hierarchy of building blocks of Figure 1 for the validation of wind-conditions models and highlights the complementarities of NEWA experiments. At the top of the pyramid, the "NEWA Meso-Micro Challenge" addresses full-system validation

towards the quantification of the accuracy and validity range of wind resource assessment methodologies. These methodologies typically integrate the long-term wind climate with site effects through a dynamical-statistical downscaling process. The underlying flow models of these methodologies improve their predictive capacity by incorporating relevant physical phenomena which are systematically validated at increasing levels of complexity as illustrated in the sidelines of the diagram.

For instance, at the lowest tier, models will try to comply with Monin-Obukhov Similarity Theory (MOST) to deal with stability-dependent wind conditions in the surface-layer under horizontally homogeneous conditions, a widely used surface boundary condition for atmospheric boundary layers. Beyond the surface layer, models would incorporate the Coriolis force and free-atmosphere conditions (capping inversion, geostrophic wind) to simulate an idealized ABL. Then, adding transient surface conditions and large-scale forcing (also called tendencies) allows simulating a realistic ABL along, for instance, a typical diurnal cycle like in the GABLS3 case [10]. Adding horizontal heterogeneity due to roughness, vegetation and elevation changes comes next with increasing complexity targeting relevant phenomena like: drastic changes of surface roughness and heat flux conditions in coastal transitions, flow above forest canopies, flow above hills from gentle to steep slopes leading to flow separation, interaction between the thermally stratified ABL and terrain at different characteristic configurations from isolated hills, hill-hill interaction, and with larger obstacles. Some of these microscale effects can be systematically studied in the controlled environment of a wind tunnel, by parametric testing of idealized topographic configurations. Different flow regimes shall be studied based on similarity parameters like the Froude number, which can explain the formation of terrain-induced effects like the blockage of the flow in front of topographic obstacles and the generation of lee (gravity) waves in stable conditions [11]. Microscale site effects in field conditions are always subject to large-scale weather phenomena that can trigger dynamic effects relevant for turbine design conditions. For example, the development of low-level jets in nocturnal conditions can lead to high wind resources but under large wind speed and directional shear (veer) across the rotor. These and many other phenomena have been traditionally studied by boundary-layer meteorologist. In the wind energy context, the main objective is to understand the relevance of these weather phenomena in the predictive capacity of wind engineering design tools.

1.3. The Ambidextrous Validation Process.

Combining validation on flow cases with integrated case studies is the objective of the ambidextrous validation process summarized in Figure 3. The challenge is reviewed by the scientific community to define the modeling approach and expected capabilities in the form of the NEWA model-chain concept statement [12] and associated validation strategy [1]. The latter identifies the relevant phenomena that should be incorporated and suitable flow cases to validate model implementations addressing these phenomena. For example, the GABLS3 benchmark [13] was used to demonstrate the validity of the “tendencies” approach for meso-micro asynchronous coupling, using general mean flow and turbulence quantities and others specific to wind energy like the rotor-equivalent wind speed (*REWS*), the wind shear, etc. This feature is then tested within wind resource assessment methodologies to quantify the impact in terms of end-

user integrated quantities of interest like annual energy prediction (*AEP*) and its associated uncertainty defined, for instance, in terms of the P_{90}/P_{50} percentile ratio of the estimated probabilistic distribution of *AEP* [14].

Figure 3: The ambidextrous validation process. (From [8], adapted to the NEWA context).

While the validation strategy for flow models considers a limited number of experiments and flow cases on the right side of the ambidextrous process, targeting specific phenomena of interest, the assessment of the performance of design tools should consider a wide range of sites in all kinds of wind climate conditions. This is eventually achieved by incorporating operational data from industry on the left-side of the validation process. This allows applying probabilistic methods to infer uncertainties in the assessment of wind conditions based on the pool of validation data. The larger the data pool, the more confidence in the predictive capacity and expected uncertainties of the tools.

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2. The Ferry Lidar Benchmark¹

Björn Witha (ForWind – University of Oldenburg), Martin Dörenkämper (Fraunhofer IWES) and Julia Gottschall (Fraunhofer IWES)

2.1. Background: The Ferry Lidar Experiment

The Ferry Lidar Experiment is one of the experiments that was conducted as part of the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) project (Mann et al, 2017).

A vertically scanning Doppler lidar was placed on a ferryboat travelling on a regular route through the Southern Baltic Sea between Kiel (Germany) and Klaipeda (Lithuania). One trip took approximately 20 hours followed by a 4 hours stopover in the harbour. During four months between February and June 2017, the Ferry Lidar continuously measured wind profiles between 65 m and 275 m above sea level along the ship track. The obtained wind profile data were corrected for ship motions (i.e. ship velocity and heading). To our knowledge this is the first dataset of wind profile measurements with lidar along such a long track.

Details about the employed ship lidar system, developed by Fraunhofer IWES, and the correction algorithm can be found in Wolken-Möhlmann et al. (2014). Further details about the NEWA Ferry Lidar Experiment can be found in the recently published article by Gottschall et al. (2018).

Figure 4: Average ship route during the Ferry Lidar Experiment (left, reproduced from Gottschall et al.(2018)) and the Fraunhofer IWES Ship Lidar System (right, © Fraunhofer IWES)

¹ Published in The Wind Vane Blog, <https://thewindvaneblog.com/the-newa-ferry-lidar-benchmark-bd79009afb26>

2.2. Motivation of the benchmark

It is common practice to evaluate mesoscale meteorological models against in-situ mast measurements of one or several met masts. With the Ferry Lidar Experiment we further develop the concept of spatially distributed wind profile measurements. The lidar moves with the ship and covers a distance that is comparable to a typical mesoscale model domain. Hence, this dataset is very suitable to be compared against meteorological mesoscale model data.

2.3. Benchmark objectives

The Ferry Lidar Benchmark is intended for mesoscale meteorological models (meso- α , meso- β scale). The objectives of the benchmark are:

- To assess how well today's mesoscale models can reproduce the wind conditions offshore and, in particular, in the Southern Baltic Sea where quite often coastal effects are present.
- To compare different models as well as different model setups of the same model against the measurements.
- To gain experience with this unique kind of data (moving wind profiles) and explore its strengths and weaknesses.

2.4. Benchmark specifications

We have planned a two-stage approach: in this first stage the participant is completely free in choosing the model setup. Use your best practice setup(s) and feel free to run more than one setup.

In a possible second stage we would prescribe part of the setup, i.e. the forcing data. This would however be announced as a separate benchmark.

The only specifications given for this first round are:

- The model domain should at least cover the full path of the ferry lidar experiment:
South-North: 54.1°N – 56.0°N
East-West: 9.8°E – 21.6°E
- The time period to be simulated is at least:
6 February – 8 June 2017

2.5. Input data

As the amount of data you will generate is too large to be uploaded somewhere, you will have to extract only the data along the ship path. We provide a python script that can be used at least as guideline how to do that. The following link leads to a cloud storage folder including the python script `interpolateWRF2ship.py` and the text file `shippath_out.csv` with the ship track during the whole campaign (time, latitude, longitude): <https://cloudstorage.uni-oldenburg.de/s/inzzrXqo5RW9WSi>

Please note that the script is designed to work with WRF output data in a specific format. You will have to modify the script so that it can work with your output. Further remarks are given in the header of the script. If you have any questions, please write to bjoern.witha@uol.de or write a comment.

2.6. Output data

Time series of wind speed, wind direction and temperature (optional) along the ship path (from the closest model grid point) for the duration of the campaign

- Time resolution of the output should be 30 min, all times in UTC
- Output in netCDF format including metadata (the extraction script requires it). To be submitted is then a csv file with the model output along the ship path (one location at a time) including the time variable (please indicate the time format!)
- Height levels: at least 100 m, if possible also: 65 m, 150 m, 200 m, 250 m.
- Information about the model and the setup (model evaluation questionnaire)

The output is to be uploaded to the following folder on our cloud storage server: <https://cloudstorage.uni-oldenburg.de/s/kEgADfW5oCKRzmL>

Please upload one zip or tar archive containing all your data and include your name and organisation in the file name.

Note that the link above is for dropping files only – you cannot see other participants' data and they cannot see your data!

2.7. Activities so far and Learning Outcomes

The benchmark was launched in October 2018. 10 different model datasets have been submitted by 7 participants. Most of the submissions have simulated with WRF, but also operational forecasts from the German Weather Service (ICON) and ECMWF (IFS) are participating and adding value to the benchmark.

Preliminary results of the benchmark have been published at the NEWA Final Workshop in Bilbao [4]. The results of the benchmark have been published in the Wind Energy Science Conference 2019 [5]. A publication in a scientific journal is in preparation.

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3. NEWA Meso-Micro Challenge for Wind Resource Assessment Phase 2: Complex Terrain²

Javier Sanz Rodrigo (CENER)

3.1. Background: The Challenge

The NEWA Meso-Micro Challenge was launched in 2018 to test wind resource assessment methodologies that blend mesoscale and microscale modeling using validation datasets generated from the NEWA experimental campaigns. The first phase was dealing with flat terrain conditions at the Cabauw site in the Netherlands [1][2] to define an initial model evaluation methodology.

3.2. Scope of Phase 2

The second phase will extend the assessment to heterogeneous terrain sites participating in the NEWA experimental campaigns, notably:

- Rödeser Berg, relatively isolated forested hill
- Hornamossen, moderately complex forested terrain
- Perdigão, double-hill covered with short canopy
- Alaiz, hill-valley-mountain

For all of these sites, data from a reference mast is provided, as in conventional wind resource assessment campaigns, to calibrate microscale models. Then, the assessment will be based on cross-validation, i.e. predicting the other measurement sites in each experiment (the target sites).

As in the first phase, the results of this benchmark will be anonymous if need be, both in terms of the name of the participant and the name of the model. Of course, it is expected that a subset of modelers will decide to publish their results with a detailed intercomparison in conferences and scientific journals.

Data Accessibility

Data from the experiments will be made available through the NEWA data server, hosted by DTU³. Observational input data will become available over the next few months when they are available for public release. In the meantime, blind benchmarks on specific flow cases are also being launched to evaluate model performance before applying wind resource methodologies.

² Published in The Wind Vane Blog, <https://thewindvaneblog.com/newa-meso-micro-challenge-phase-2-complex-terrain-98efeb03a23a>

³ <https://doi.org/10.11583/DTU.c.4508597.v1>

3.3. Objectives

The objectives of the Meso-Micro challenge apply in this second phase as follows:

- Test meso-micro methodologies consistently for a range of wind climates and terrain conditions and map accuracy vs cost for relevant quantities of interest, notably for annual energy production (AEP) and other siting parameters (turbulence intensity, wind shear, etc).
- Establish open-access practices for the assessment of these methodologies that can determine the added value of meso-micro with respect to conventional methods based on microscale modeling only.
- Discuss methodologies for uncertainty estimation of gross AEP and discuss their adequacy to the wind resource assessment process used by industry.

3.4. Input data

Observations

One year of observations from the reference masts are provided in netCDF format. A reference period of one year is considered for each site in order to cover seasonal wind variability. For data quality purposes and to facilitate the participation of high-fidelity models, the assessment will be focused on prevailing wind direction sectors, free of wake effects or mast distortion, although results for the other sectors can also be included for completeness.

All these reference input data is provided within a dedicated document for each site.

Elevation and Land Cover

High-resolution maps of elevation and canopy characteristics from aerial lidar scans are provided in netCDF format for each site.

Mesoscale Forcing

If you only plan to run microscale simulations based on mesoscale input data, for consistency purposes, we would like you to use the mesoscale input forcing provided, which is based on the WRF configuration that has been used to generate the European Wind Atlas.

Mesoscale input forcing in terms of mesoscale tendencies is provided for all the sites following the same methodology of the GABSL3 benchmark case and described in [3].

A netCDF file for mesoscale data is provided with the following information:

- Site coordinates and Coriolis parameter (fc).
- Time-height 2D arrays of velocity components (U, V, W) and potential temperature (Th).
- Time-height 2D arrays of mesoscale forcings (tendencies): geostrophic wind (Ug, Vg), advective wind ($Uadv, Vadv$) and advective potential temperature ($Thadv$).

- Time array of surface-layer quantities: friction velocity (ust), kinematic heat flux (wt), 2-m temperature ($T2$), skin temperature (TSK), surface pressure ($Psfc$).

Units, dimensions and variables description are all provided in the netCDF file. Momentum tendencies are provided in [$m\ s^{-1}$] and should be multiplied by the Coriolis parameter to obtain appropriate forces in [$m\ s^{-2}$]. For convenience, we have omitted information about humidity since the assumption of dry-atmosphere is typically adopted by wind energy flow models.

Reference Power Curve

The NREL 5 MW reference power curve will be used to evaluate AEP [4]. This will be computed in the evaluation process based on the wind speed distributions.

3.5. Validation Data

Cross-validation will be carried out using the wind characteristics of the reference site for normalization purposes. The following quantities of interest will be evaluated:

- Horizontal wind speed (S) relative to the reference site (S/S_0).
- Gross AEP based on the reference power curve.
- Turbulence intensity based on the turbulent kinetic energy (tke).
- Wind shear exponent (α).

Validation results will be visualized using, for instance:

- Distributions binned by wind direction and stability.
- Scattered plots (observed vs predicted).
- Vertical profiles and longitudinal transects.

Stability classification will be based on the z/L parameter, where L is the Obukhov length, measured in the surface-layer (in the 10 m range) at the reference site. This is general convention but other methods based on temperature gradient (Ri or Fr) could be tested as well. For guidance, stability classes are defined as follows:

- Unstable (u): $-0.6 < z/L < -0.2$
- Neutral (n): $-0.02 < z/L < 0.02$
- Stable (s): $0.2 < z/L < 0.6$

Wind direction will be binned using 30° intervals (12 sectors). You can provide full 360° distributions or focus on the reference sectors defined in each benchmark.

3.6. Model Runs

Consistent with the philosophy of the challenge, each participant should develop a plan to span the accuracy vs cost figure. For instance:

A WRF modeler could run yearly simulations starting from the 3-nest configuration of the reference set-up (or a different one) and add other 3 nests switching to LES down to

resolutions of the order of 100 m and provide 6 results, one from each nest, for the 3 sites.

A CFD modeler may vary the number of simulations in terms of e.g. resolutions or boundary conditions included in the assessment.

Calibration

Adopting the end-user perspective, the simulations should consider how to best use on-site measurements to calibrate the model-chain to the reference mast. This is equivalent to the conventional micrositing process in the design phase of ensuring that self-prediction at the reference site is free of bias before extrapolating horizontally or vertically to other target prediction sites.

Parameterization of RANS models

For consistency with the GABLS3 benchmark, microscale models using Sogachev et al. (2012) k - ϵ turbulence model shall use this set of constants: $\kappa = 0.4$, $C_{\epsilon 1} = 1.52$, $C_{\epsilon 2} = 1.833$, $\sigma_{\kappa} = 2.95$, $\sigma_{\epsilon} = 2.95$ and $C_{\mu} = 0.03$ [5].

3.7. Output Data

The ultimate goal is to evaluate annual quantities, as described in the validation section, derived by bin-averaging from model simulations from relevant wind direction sectors and stability classes. To homogenize the output data please consider these indications:

- One NetCDF file per site and per simulation run including all the validation positions grouped by “profiles”.
- Each profile is defined in terms of 3D tables, where the third index denotes the stability class (1 = ‘u’, 2 = ‘n’, 3 = ‘s’), the first index refers to a point in the profile (identified by an ID number) and the second index provides the value for the following bin-averaged quantities. Hence, for each stability class, the following 2D tables will be generated:

$$ID, x, y, z, f1, S1, WD1, tke1, \dots, f12, S12, WD12, tke12$$

where x, y, z are coordinates of a sensor location in the microscale map, with z being the height above ground level, f being the frequency of the corresponding bin, and the subscripts denote the wind direction sector number.

“Profiles” are typically vertical profiles at target mast locations (fixed x and y , varying z), longitudinal transects (fixed z , varying x and y) or, simply, a point cloud associated to target evaluation locations. In any case, you are supposed to interpolate your results to each x, y, z coordinates so that the dimensions of the tables are consistent for all participants. A list of profiles is defined for each site and provided as part of the input data files.

A python script is provided to support you writing your data to the correct netCDF format. Please respect the naming convention for variables to allow automatic post-processing.

Together with the output data you should provide a summary of your model set-up and methodology to extract the bin-averaged output quantities.

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4. NEWA Meso-Micro Challenge for Wind Resource Assessment Phase 2: Rödeser Berg⁴

Martin Dörenkämper (Fraunhofer IWES)

4.1. Background: The Rödeser Berg Experiment

The Forested Hill Experiment Kassel was conducted within the EU project NEWA – New European Wind Atlas (ERA-NET Plus, topic FP7-ENERGY.2013.10.1.2). Information about the experiment can be found in Kühn et al, 2018 [1].

Site Description

This field campaign provides a unique dataset of wind measurements for validating models for flow over forested hilly terrain. The experiment was conducted on the Rödeser Berg, a hill (380m height) near Kassel, Germany (Figure 5). In October 2016, a three-month intensive campaign relying heavily on remote sensing devices, i.e. lidar and sodar wind measurement systems, marked the beginning of the experiment. At the same time a one-year long-term campaign using two tall masts started.

Figure 5: Location of the Rödeser Berg site in central Germany.

The Rödeser Berg site is located in the federal state Hesse (Germany), around 20 km northwest of the city of Kassel. The terrain height is between 200 m and 400 m (hill top) (Figure 6 – left). The hill site is characterized by broadleaf forests with some spots of coniferous wood. Tree heights are around 20-35 m (Figure 6 – right). The roughness length in the area is in the range of 0.03 to 0.75 m (Figure 7).

⁴ Published in The Wind Vane Blog, <https://thewindvaneblog.com/newa-meso-micro-challenge-phase-2-r%C3%B6deser-berg-5404eafbe7dc>

Figure 6: Topography of the site (left) as well as forest heights in the same area (right). The red dot marks the position of the 200m met mast on top of the Rödeseer Berg. Data Source (ALS data): Hessische Verwaltung für Bodenmanagement und Geoinformation]

Figure 7: Roughness length distribution [based on CORINE-Dataset – EEA (2016)], converted to roughness lengths with the method by Silva, et. al 2007 [2]

In Spring of 2015 a wind farm, consisting of four Enercon E 101 (3MW, rotor diameter: 101m, hub height 35m) became operational at the site. These turbines are located northwest of the 200m met mast on the hill-top.

The benchmarks will provide a one year time series of one met mast (reference) and ask for prediction of the wind conditions at a different point in terrain where the second met mast (target) operated. The target met mast data will not be provided in order to emulate a realistic modelling situation typical in site assessment.

The two met masts are located at the following positions:

Table 1: Positions of the two met masts used for the benchmark.

Met Mast Name	Easting (UTM Zone 32) [m]	Northing (UTM Zone 32) [m]	Terrain Height [m]	Measurement Heights [m]
MM140 (reference)	511589.36	5687521.12	261.0	80,135
MM200 (target)	513590.52	5690182.54	388.0	80, 135, 200

4.2. Input Data

All input data is provided via b2drop and can be accessed via the following link:
<https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/6AsjPnRL8x7KBHk>

Namely, the input data set consists of terrain data (including terrain height and forest information) as well as met mast time series. Mesoscale forcing data can be provided by the NEWA consortium upon request.

Terrain Data

Terrain data (terrain height, inclination, forest height, forest density) is provided in netCDF format for an 8 x 8 km patch in a resolution of 10 m. In addition, aerodynamic roughness data based on CORINE is provided. The simulation domain does not necessarily need to be fixed to this patch. Feel free to use your best practice approach and reduce/increase the domain size with other data sources (e.g. lower resolution satellite data) if needed.

Met Mast Time Series

A one year time series (31.10.2016–30.10.2017) from one of the two met mast (MM140) is provided. This time series consists of wind speed at two heights (80m and 135m), wind direction (80m) and the dimensionless Obukhov length (20m/L) in a single netCDF file. The data of the second evaluation point is hold back. For a correct and fair evaluation it was made sure that data from both masts and all relevant sensors are available at every time step. This explains the comparatively large number of missing values of the time series provided.

Mesoscale Forcing (optional)

Mesoscale forcing data for the simulation period from WRF simulations can be provided by CENER upon request. Please contact Javier Sanz Rodrigo in case you need or want to use this data for setting up your modelling approach.

4.3. Output Data

The ultimate goal is to provide annual quantities, derived by bin-averaging model simulations from relevant wind direction sectors and stability classes. To homogenize the output data please consider these indications:

- One netCDF file per site and per simulation run including both of the two validation positions grouped by “profiles”.
- Each profile is defined in terms of 3D tables, where the third index denotes the stability class (1 = ‘u’, 2 = ‘n’, 3 = ‘s’), the first index refers to a point in the profile (identified by an ID number) and the second index provides the value for the following bin-averaged quantities. Hence, for each stability class, the following 2D tables will be generated:

ID, x, y, z, f1, S1, WD1, tke1, ... , f12, S12, WD12, tke12

where x, y, z are coordinates of a sensor location in the microscale map, with z being the height above ground level, f being the frequency of the corresponding bin, and the subscripts denote the wind direction sector number.

The binning of the results should be done in 30 degree windows and three stability classes. We suggest the following binning:

- WD = 15, 45, 75, ..., 345° (30 degree steps, centered on middle)
- Unstable: $z/L < -0.05$
- Neutral: $-0.05 < z/L < 0.05$
- Stable: $z/L > 0.05$

The evaluation will focus on the bins 195, 225, 255° to neglect the impact of wakes on the wind conditions. However, you are invited to provide data for all bins.

A python3 script is provided (see Link given in section Input data) to support you writing your data to the correct netCDF format. Please respect the naming convention for variables to allow automatic post-processing.

Together with the output data you should provide a summary of your model set-up and methodology to extract the bin-averaged output quantities.

All data (i.e. the netCDF Output data and the model setup description) should be uploaded in a single zip file to the following directory:

<https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/e26nOxeKCKE8R2L>

4.4. Results and Outlook

The results of the benchmark have been published in the Wind Energy Science Conference 2019. A publication of the benchmark results in a journal paper is planned afterwards.

The NEWA meso-micro challenge will continue in the frame of the IEA-Wind Task 31 “Wakebench” as new benchmarks are generated from the NEWA database of experiments.

4.5. References

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